

Abstract

Fetal development of the optical system will result in unavoidable variation. Hebbian processes help reduce this effect within the optic nerve in utero but are very limited in how much can be done with retinal rod-cone placement and neuron routing or optic nerve to visual cortex generated image. This theoretical model suggests refinements occur after birth by image and time based refinement of the image details using the full visual system. Refinement in pointing angle is made by successive sharp edged blocks of high contrast moving across the visual field and detecting timing error of individual neurons to correct their placement in the visual field. Current understanding in the field focuses on stages of eye tracking changes by month after birth. This theoretical model suggests changes in infant vision growth by changing aspects of the development environment. These changes should produce testable changes in speed of currently measured eye tracking development speed.

Current State of the Field

Retinotopic mapping: is not applied before birth or for several months after birth. This theoretical model covers the time between birth and early retinotopic mapping and explains why retinotopic mappings show such adult like responses.

Activity-dependent refinement: during the first few months after birth the strength, control, and presumed kinesthetic reporting of muscle movement is too crude to help with refinement at this level.

Critical period development: This model helps refine stages and causes of progression of the critical periods.

Orientation columns: This theoretical model suggests refinement of Orientation columns, but works within the existing scope.

Ocular dominance columns: This theoretical model deals primarily with refining the visual process to make binocular vision more feasible, before ocular dominance columns becomes prominent.

Current practice on understanding human infant visual development seems more a catalog of large scale steps or stages, and usually only things that can be measured by looking angle measured by eye tracking devices, without an underlying theory of how the infant changes to produce the eye tracking data and schedules reported. Possibly a more detailed theory of the how and not just the what and when may help in further improving infant visual development and helping individuals with loss of vision do better visual recovery.

This model covers early infant visual imaging refinement using high contrast boundaries of external object motion and early motion induced boundary movement to refine local temporal spatial coherence to improve geometric accuracy. This model extends known principles of activity-dependent refinement by proposing that early incoherence in fine spatial mapping is reduced through an external object motion-based edge alignment process that allows transition timing of individual photoreceptors during movement of high contrast, sharply defined regions to refine photoreceptor to visual cortex mapping.

When the fetus is growing and building the optic nerve it is difficult to understand how the approximately 126 million photoreceptors have an exact match between ends of every optic nerve so

that photoreceptor locations on the retina exactly matched their attachments to the visual processing centers in the brain. Normal variations during healthy growth are likely to creep in to cause a less than fully coherent connection between retinas and visual cortex. It is assumed that Hebbian processes take neuron firing in utero will help align neural connections but not be able to handle all the fine details of routing neurons on the retina from optic nerve to rods and cones to difference between spatial connections to the visual cortex and how the visual cortex interprets those locations to be in the visual field. Both processes can only be adjusted by using the entire visual path: object to light, light to lens, lens focusing onto retina, location of rods and cones on retina, rods and cones connecting to neurons, neurons traveling down optic nerve, optic nerve connecting to visual cortex, visual cortex mapping those sensations into a visual image.

My proposal is that they do not start out as an exact match, just a moderately good match with some outliers. That the process of converting this blurry, inaccurate vision system into the highly accurate and detailed vision most adults have occurs during the first months of infancy and finish, or come close to finishing early enough that we don't remember it happening at all.

What I propose is that starting with the blurry but mostly close with some outliers images the brain is able to calibrate the pointing angle, and possibly the size of the field of view of each photoreceptor using only the timed sequences of perceived images of moving objects/transitions. When areas of high contrast move across the infant's field of view there is a progress movement of a dark to light or light to dark line across the retina. When the brain detects the time of each neuron firing when it perceives the location to be inside a region of the opposite response it then 'adjusts' effective perceived location to be close to the dividing line between the photoreceptors currently transitioning between light and dark areas. By waiting until the neuron goes from opposite to same and moving the assumed location to the nearest part of the dividing line the revised pointing angle can be more accurate with each moving sharp, moving transition. The process improves local spatial temporal correlation. The same process applied to small difference to when a neuron changes to keep up with the others around it with assumed similar pointing angles. Successive passes will continue to refine the neuron to pointing angle map to converge on geometric accuracy. This process needs high contrast divisions moving across the eyes in every direction to make adjustments in both axes.

This process is best done with little to no eye movement so that the only changes are the movement of the external objects. As the mapping becomes more accurate the visual system can begin making more useful image based visual object centroids/reticles to sense movement even when such movement is the head turning or the eye tracking and continue the process of migrating photoreceptors mapping in the field of view. With this limited degree of accuracy these self movements may not be kinesthetically well defined but still useful with image based image processing improvement. In fact the ability to add eye movement to the refinement process can add movement in directions or areas not well represented in early vision.

The calibration of color is more subtle. Since three different cones are needed for each perceived location and the grouping is unlikely to be a regular array of alternating triplets the brain must learn the relative positions and probably require working out a way to use several nearby cones of different clusters to find an averaging function for each one to develop a color for each one, or at least every grouping. This probably has to wait until the monochrome calibration is done enough to work with the very fine level of pointing angle needed to provide their complex weighting functions to combine a small group of cones into a single color.

The mechanism for this pointing angle is not clear a speculation that adding and pruning dendrite connections could simplify this stage of correction. However other effects such as wearing inversion glasses, color or darkness changing glasses such as sun glasses have shown the brain's ability to correct even such major changes within a few days. This is assumed to be another example of neuroplasticity. However this process is on a very fine resolution level and very permanent, changing only over years or decades, so it might be slightly different than a neuroplasticity change which can occur in days not months, and be reversible and multi-valued almost instantly if the changes continue occurring back and forth or switching between three or more states.

If correct this proposal would help explain the causes of the change in a baby's eye tracking over the months. Also there is no advantage to improving depth of field or distance vision until visual calibration makes it possible to detect out of focus condition or be able to discern small or distant objects. Until both focus and visual calibration are well advanced binocular tracking and 2D to 3D vision is difficult.

Conclusions. For assisting infant visual processing improvement starting with high contrast, black and white objects with simple, straight line borders in the first several months followed by the brightly colored, deeply saturated strong, simple transitions for the next several months seem to be likely to be helpful. Ensuring that throughout this process the movement changes direction and covers the entire field of view. The motion should initially be slow enough for processing the images to determine what corrections need to be made. Increasing the speed without losing interest may improve the rate of progress. Switching to bright primary colors will help locate the pointing angle for each color cones, then mixing primary only with increasingly desaturated colors to begin balancing the groups of colors to produce more accurate single colors so that later teaching the names of colors will have a more solid foundation to work with.